

TOURISM SUPPLY AND DEMAND

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Abstract: Tourism demand is a broad term that covers the factors governing the level of demand, the spatial characteristics of demand, different types of demand and the motives for making such demands.

Keywords: Tour, Company, Demand, Supply, Market.

Introduction.

There are as many reasons for engaging in tourism, as there are tourists.

Different people participate in tourism for different purposes. Seemingly, every purpose comes with specific tourism demand. One of the most common demands is for accommodation. Whatever the intention, tourists should be accommodated in one way or another. The most common reasons for travel away from home are:

- For leisure, recreation and holidays
- To visit friends and relatives
- For business and professional engagements
- For health treatment
- To undertake religious and other pilgrimages
- Other more personal motives

The demand for tourism can be defined in various ways, depending on the economic, psychological, geographic and political point of view of the author. The geographic perspective defines tourism demand as the total number of persons who travel or wish to travel, and use tourist facilities and services at places away from their places of work or residence (Cooper et al. 1993). One of the important issues relating to tourism as mentioned in a number of official proclamations, demands is the individual's right. In 1980 the Manila Declaration on World Tourism stated that the ultimate aim of tourism was "the improvement of the quality of life and the creation of better living conditions for all people" (Cooper et al. 1993: 14). This sentiment is reflected in the tourism vision as stated in the 1996 South Africa Government's White Paper on Tourism. Cooper et al. (1993) identified two types of demand curves. The first one is the direct demand curve that states that a tourism product can be ascribed to the relationship between two variables like 'price' and 'quantity'. This is a relationship in the economic demand schedule. The second one is the inverse

demand curve that states that the quantity of demand for tourism drops with an increase in the price associated with tourism, and vice versa.

Tourism supply has to do with the provision of the key elements of the tourism industry by the host governments or destinations. Such provision should extend to maintenance, promotion and management of the tourism facilities and resources. Tourism resources that are necessary for tourism supply range from natural to man-made. Infrastructure required would include telecommunication, accommodation and transportation. Tourism reception services include travel agencies, tourist offices, hire companies and visitor managers. The one underlying characteristic of tourism supply that distinguishes it from other services is the way in which the mobile population who visit destination areas consume a tourism product, service or experience. In contrast, the supply elements are often fixed geographically at certain places (e.g. hotels, restaurants or visitor attractions). This means that businesses are required to sink considerable capital costs into different forms of tourism services and centres of production on the basis of the expectation that the destination will appeal to visitors and assist in the promotion of their individual product and service.

The “tourism supply chain” concept originated from economics. It has been used to explain how different businesses enter into contractual relationships to supply services, products and goods, and how these goods are assembled into products at different points in the supply chain. Tourism is well suited in the supply chain because the product, service or experience that is consumed is assembled and comprises a wide range of suppliers.

The supply of tourism products basically involves how various components of the tourist product are placed at the disposal of tourists. Tourism suppliers can be classified under the following headings: Hospitality, Transport and Attractions/Products. As far as hospitality is concerned, this is where a tourist will look at the appropriate forms of accommodation, different types of food service provisioning, entertainment and leisure activities. The suppliers of hospitality products, such as accommodation, service, entertainment or gaming must be well located in relation to other components of tourism product. The suppliers of accommodation vary from privately owned organisations to large hotel chain groups or consortiums. On the other hand, the food service industry, which includes drinking places, restaurants, coffee shops and other food outlets, is strongly linked to the accommodation sector. Ultimately, accommodation

forms the core of the tourism supply chain where it occupies a more central position.

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